

ELECTROMECHANICAL RESPONSE OF MULTIFUNCTIONAL PIEZOELECTRIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this study, multifunctional composites made of various material combinations have been studied. Three dimensional finite element models are developed to completely characterize the electromechanical response of multifunctional composite structures. Previous study by the authors was focused on 3-3 type piezoelectric foam structure made up of PZT-7A with asymmetric interconnects, symmetric interconnects and without any interconnecting struts. The present work extends the piezoelectric foam structures to multifunctional composite structures by enclosing the foam structures with symmetric interconnect made of PZT-7A (acts as first phase) within piezoelectric materials (acts as second phase); (i) barium titanate (BaTiO_3), and relaxor ferroelectrics (PMN-33%PT) (ceramic-ceramic piezoelectric composites), and (ii) polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) (ceramic-polymer piezoelectric composites). The various piezoelectric composite systems used in this study were chosen to represent a wide range of practical applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

Porous piezoelectric ceramics have improved performance such as high dielectric constant, and high hydrostatic figures of merits (d_h , g_h and $d_h g_h$) [1-8]. But due to their typical ceramic behaviour (i.e. brittle behaviour) and difficulty in poling, piezoelectric composite materials, usually made of piezoelectric ceramics and passive polymers, are gaining importance because piezoelectric composites mitigate some of limitations of monolithic piezoelectric ceramics [9]. Piezoelectric composites are promising materials for transducer applications, and they are widely used in high-pressure sensors, underwater hydrophones, biomedical imaging, and non-destructive testing applications [10].

A few studies [1-8] have considered the electromechanical response of porous piezoelectric ceramics with different types of porosity (i.e. 3-0, 3-1 or 3-3). More recently, Singh et al. [6] studied the electromechanical response of 3-0, 3-1 and 3-3 porosity type piezoelectric foams structures made up of PZT-7A and relaxor ferroelectric (PMN-PT based) and found out that 3-3 type porous piezoelectric foam structures made of relaxor ferroelectrics has extremely high hydrostatic figures of merits such as d_h , g_h and $d_h g_h$ as compared to 3-0 and 3-1 type porous piezoelectric structures. Bosse et al. [7] benchmark importance of 3-3 type piezoelectric foam structures, as these structures have been proven to show high figure of merits such as d_h , g_h and $d_h g_h$. Challagulla and Venkatesh [8] demonstrated that 3-3 type porous piezoelectric structure with asymmetric interconnects, symmetric interconnects, and without any interconnecting struts can exhibit enhanced elastic, piezoelectric coefficients, dielectric coefficients and hydrostatic figure of merits, hence suitable for hydrophone applications.

The understanding of effective behaviour of piezoelectric composites consisting of inclusion/fibers and matrix phases has received considerable attention during the past decades. Piezoelectric composites structures are extensively studied through experimental methods [9-12], analytical techniques [13-17] and numerical modeling [18-22] to predict and simulate the linear coupled

piezoelectric and mechanical behaviour of piezoelectric composites. For example, Yoon et al. [9] fabricated transverse 1-3 piezoelectric ceramic/polymer composite using multi-layer piezoelectric blocks method and measured various effective piezoelectric coefficients. Chen and Wu [11] used sintering technique to fabricate PZT/polymer composite with 3-3 connectivity and studied the effect of three-kinds of polymer materials and polymer hardness on 3-3 piezoelectric composite. Lin et al. [12] used viscous polymer processing technique for fabrication of piezoelectric fiber composites.

Classification of various piezoelectric composites is given by Newnham et al. [13] based on the connectivity of the constituent phases and formulated series-parallel model to derive effective fundamental constants of piezocomposites. Challagulla and Venkatesh [14] developed micromechanical model based on asymptotic homogenization technique to predict complete electromechanical response of 2-2 layered piezoelectric composites consisting of ceramic-ceramic (PZT 7A-BaTiO₃) and ceramic-polymer (PZT 7A-PVDF) system. Kar Gupta and Venkatesh [15] developed analytical model to predicted electromechanical response of 1-3 type piezoelectric composites. Guinovart-Diaz et al. [16] derived analytical expressions for 1-3 piezoelectric composites. Della and Shu [17] developed micromechanics method to investigate the performance of 1-3 piezoelectric composites with a porous non-piezoelectric matrix using Mori-Tanaka (MT) method.

In conjunction with experimental and analytical models, several studies have focused on developing numerical models to predict the effective electromechanical behaviour of piezoelectric composites. Zhang and Wu [18] developed finite element model using finite element software ABAQUS to study the effect of connectivity and shape of constituents phase of piezoelectric composites representing 3-0, 3-1, 3-2 and 3-3 type connectivity with piezoelectric fiber in polymer phase or reverse on the effective material coefficients. Kar-Gupta and Venkatesh [19] presented unit-cell based finite element modelling to capture electromechanical response of piezoelectric composites with 0-3, 1-3, 2-2 and 3-3 connectivity made up of ceramic-polymer (BaTiO₃-PVDF) system using finite element software ABAQUS, and also demonstrated that geometric connectivity of active phase in piezoelectric composites has significant influence on effective properties of piezoelectric composites. More recently, Kar Gupta and Venkatesh [20] developed finite element model and analytical model (based on asymptotic homogenization technique) to predict electromechanical response of 2-2 piezoelectric composites and finite element results were found to be in good agreement with analytical results. Pettermann and Suresh [21] developed unit-cell based finite element model for 1-3 type piezoelectric composite structure with periodic arrangement of continuous aligned fibers. Lewis et al. [22] captured electromechanical response of 3-3 type piezocomposite structure with PZT 5H-Air (representing porous piezoelectric system) and PZT 5H-Polymer with polymer such as polyethylene and epoxy (representing ceramic-polymer system) using commercial finite element software ANSYS.

In addition to analytical, numerical, and experimental studies on piezoelectric composites, several studies have focused on analysing piezoelectric composites made up of different piezoelectric materials [23-26] (such as barium titanate (BaTiO₃)/polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) [23, 24] and relaxor ferroelectrics (RL) [25, 26]). For example, Kar-Gupta and Venkatesh [23] used two combination of fiber/matrix (PZT-7A as fiber and BaTiO₃ as matrix, and PZT-7A as fiber/PVDF as matrix) to develop finite element model of 1-3 piezoelectric composite using ABAQUS. Della and Shu [24] studied 1-3 piezoelectric composite with active ceramic (PZT-7A, BaTiO₃) and passive polymer matrix (Araldite D, P(VDF-TrFE)), and found out that hydrostatic response (i.e. d_h , g_h and $d_h g_h$) is better when P(VDF-TrFE) passive polymer is used in combination with PZT-7A. Lam and Chan [25] fabricated 65PMN-35PT/P(VDF-TrFE) based 0-3 type piezocomposites with different volume fraction of Relaxor ferroelectrics (PMN-PT based), and composites with high PMN-PT volume fraction found to have higher piezoelectric coefficients. Li et al. [26] explained importance of relaxor ferroelectrics (PMN-PT based) piezocomposites over traditional PZT 1-3 type piezocomposites by fabricating PIN-PMN-PT single crystal based 1-3 type piezocomposites using dice and fill method.

Overall several analytical, numerical and experimental studies have demonstrated that piezoelectric composites exhibit a combination of properties that are desirable for practical applications such as medical imaging, sensors, actuators and hydrophones. However, a comprehensive study on the effects of interconnected struts and simultaneously piezoelectric material properties in a range of piezoelectric material systems (Table 1) such as barium titanate, polyvinylidene fluoride, and relaxor ferroelectrics (PMN-33%PT) on the overall electromechanical response of multifunctional piezoelectric composite (Fig. 1) have not been studied. Hence the objectives of present study are:

- (i) to develop a unit-cell based finite element model to predict complete elastic, dielectric and piezoelectric properties of other various multifunctional piezoelectric composites;
- (ii) to study the effects of variation of interconnect strut lengths (i.e. F2 with $L=0.4l$, F3 with $0.8l$ and F4 with $1.5l$, where l =internal cube length), volume fraction and simultaneously the fundamental piezoelectric material properties on the effective electromechanical response of multifunctional piezoelectric composites;
- (iii) to assess the effects of interconnect strut lengths, volume fraction and simultaneously the fundamental piezoelectric material properties on the effective figures of merit of multifunctional piezoelectric composites.

The present work is organised as follows. An overview of the constitutive relations that describe the coupled behaviour of piezoelectric materials is presented in Section 2. Section 3 briefly describes the finite element model developed to characterize the electromechanical response of piezoelectric composites. The trends observed are presented in Section 4 and finally, Section 5 concludes the work.

	PZT-7A ($\rho = 7700$ kg/m ³)	BaTiO ₃ ($\rho = 5700$ kg/m ³)	PVDF ($\rho = 1780$ Kg/m ³)	PMN-33%PT ($\rho = 8060$ Kg/m ³)	Air ($\rho = 1.025$ Kg/m ³)
C_{11}^L (GPa)	148	150.4	4.84	115	0
C_{12}^L (GPa)	74.2	65.94	2.22	102	0
C_{13}^L (GPa)	76.2	65.6	2.72	103	0
C_{22}^L (GPa)	131	145.5	4.63	103	0
C_{23}^L (GPa)	74.2	65.94	2.22	102	0
C_{33}^L (GPa)	148	150.4	4.84	115	0
C_{11}^E (GPa)	25.3	43.86	0.052	69	0
C_{33}^E (GPa)	35.9	42.37	1.06	66	0
C_{EE}^E (GPa)	25.3	43.86	0.052	69	0
e_{1E} (C/m ²)	9.31	11.40	-0.0019	10.1	0
e_{21} (C/m ²)	-2.324	-4.320	0.0043	-3.9	0
e_{22} (C/m ²)	10.9	17.40	-0.1099	20.3	0
e_{23} (C/m ²)	-2.324	-4.320	0.0043	-3.9	0
e_{3E} (C/m ²)	9.31	11.40	-0.0019	10.1	0
κ_{11}^E (10^{-9} C ² /Nm ²)	3.98	12.80	0.0664	12.7	8.854e-3
κ_{22}^E (10^{-9} C ² /Nm ²)	2.081	15.10	0.0708	6.02	8.854e-3
κ_{33}^E (10^{-9} C ² /Nm ²)	3.98	12.80	0.0664	12.7	8.854e-3

Table 1. Fundamental elastic, dielectric, and piezoelectric properties of the model materials (lead zirconate titanate (PZT-7A) [14], barium titanate (BaTiO₃) [14], polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) [14], relaxor ferroelectrics (PMN-33%PT) [27], and Air) chosen for the present study.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of four kinds of 3-3 type multifunctional piezoelectric composite structures; (a) without any interconnects (F1), (b) with asymmetric interconnects (F2, F3, and F4) considered in the present study.

2 CONSTITUTIVE RELATIONS FOR PIEZOELECTRIC MATERIALS

The constitutive relations for a piezoelectric material that exhibits coupling between mechanical and electrical properties are given by [7]:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma \\ D \end{pmatrix} = \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} C^E & -e^T \\ e & \kappa^\epsilon \end{pmatrix}}_M \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon \\ E \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where σ is second-order stress tensor, ϵ is second-order strain tensor, C^E is fourth-order elasticity tensor with superscript ‘‘E’’ indicating elasticity tensor corresponding to measurement of C at constant/zero electric field, D is electric displacement vector, E is the electric field vector and κ^ϵ is second-order permittivity tensor measured at constant/zero strain. Eq. (1) is the most general representation of the constitutive behaviour of piezoelectric materials and has 21 elasticity, 18 piezoelectric and 6 permittivity constants that are independent material properties. Thus a complete characterization of piezoelectric foam in the linear elastic domain requires an identification of all 45 independent constants [7].

Four important figures of merit, i.e. the piezoelectric coupling constant ($K_r = \sqrt{1 - C_{22}^b/C_{22}^0}$), the acoustic impedance ($Z = \sqrt{\rho C_{22}^0}$), the hydrostatic strain coefficient ($d_h = d_{22} + d_{21} + d_{23}$) and the hydrostatic figure of merit (d_{hg}), are typically invoked to assess the utility of piezoelectric composites in practical applications.

3 FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

Commercially available finite element software named ABAQUS, has been used to develop unit-cell based finite element model to determine all the 45 independent material constants and the figures of merit of multifunctional piezoelectric composites over a range of volume fraction, fundamental material properties, and interconnect lengths (F1, F2, F3 and F4). Eight-node, linear piezoelectric brick elements (C3D8E) are utilized for the piezoelectric composite structures where each node is allowed four degrees of freedom (three translational and one electric potential). As the unit cell is expected to capture the electromechanical response of composite system, particular care has been taken in invoking boundary conditions to ensure that the electromechanical deformation characteristics of the microscopic unit cells under conditions of electric and mechanical loading are representative of the deformation of the macroscopic piezocomposite structures. It is assumed that the piezoelectric material is poled in 2-direction. The applied electric field is assumed to be large enough that can polarize the entire material in the poling direction but small enough to prevent dielectric breakdown of the material.

To ensure that the deformation and electric potential across the boundaries of the representative unit cell is compatible with the deformation of the adjacent unit cells, the following constraint equations are identified (Fig. 2), where the nodes A (AA), B (BB), C (CC), D (DD) are designated as master nodes and u refers to all four degrees of freedom (i.e., $u = 1, 2, 3$ and 9):

- (i) For periodicity in 1-direction: $u^R - u^A = u^S - u^B$; $u^{RR} - u^{AA} = u^{SS} - u^{BB}$;
 $u^V - u^A = u^W - u^B$; $u^{VV} - u^{DD} = u^{WW} - u^{CC}$; and $u^{XM} - u^A = u^{XP} - u^B$
- (ii) For periodicity in 2-direction: $u^U - u^A = u^{UU} - u^{AA}$; $u^S - u^B = u^{SS} - u^{BB}$;
 $u^{YM} - u^A = u^{YP} - u^{AA}$
- (iii) For periodicity in 3-direction: $u^T - u^D = u^U - u^A$, $u^{TT} - u^{DD} = u^{UU} - u^{AA}$,
 $u^W - u^B = u^{WW} - u^C$; $u^{ZM} - u^B = u^{ZP} - u^C$

Figure 2: Schematic representation of various node sets identified for the finite element modeling of 3-3 type multifunctional piezoelectric composite structures.

By observing the electromechanical response of a particular unit cell to a series of controlled mechanical and electrical loading conditions, all the 45 material constants that correspond to particular composite are identified. A key feature of the present model is that all the 4 types of unit cells (F1, F2, F3 and F4) are subjected to one general set of periodic boundary conditions for all loading conditions. Additionally, perfect bonding between two phases has been assumed.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The numerical model developed in the present study is first applied to composite structure F1 (with an external strut length equal to zero ($L=0$)) and composite structure F2 (with strut length equal to 0.4 times the internal cube dimension ($L= 0.4l$)) where the struts are made of isotropic material (non-piezoelectric, carbon) with young's modulus (E) of 15.61GPa and poisson's ratio (ν) of 0.33 and enclosed within air [28] ($\epsilon_r=1$, stiffness= 0). The results are compared with analytical models [29-32] available in the literature for isotropic (non-piezoelectric) open-cell foams. It is evident that there is reasonable agreement and some differences in the predictions of the analytical models and finite element models. Some of analytical models, for example Gibson and Ashby [29] and Warren and Kraynik [30] assumed struts undergo only bending deformations, Christensen [31] assumed that struts undergo axial deformation, Li et al. [32] considered three deformations (i.e. stretching, shearing, and bending). However, finite element model presented in this study assumed struts undergo bending and axial deformations.

Fig. 3 presents the variation of fundamental elastic, piezoelectric and dielectric constants of various piezoelectric structures (i.e. F1, F2, F3 and F4) for four piezoelectric systems (BaTiO₃-PZT, PVDF-PZT, RL-PZT and Air-PZT) with increasing PZT material volume fraction. In the ceramic-ceramic (i.e. BaTiO₃-PZT and RL-PZT) multifunctional piezoelectric composite system, the elastic, piezoelectric and dielectric properties vary linearly with volume fraction of the first phase (PZT-7A) except some shear piezoelectric coefficients such as e_{16} , e_{21} , e_{23} , e_{34} for piezoelectric composite structure F1 ($L=0$) made up of RL-PZT composite, which varies non-linearly with increase in volume fraction of PZT-7A. On the other hand, in the polymer-ceramic (where outside material is softer i.e. PVDF-PZT) and air-ceramic (i.e. Air-PZT) multifunctional piezoelectric composite system, the elastic, and piezoelectric properties vary non-linearly with volume fraction of the first phase i.e. PZT-7A. Whereas dielectric properties of these piezoelectric composites still vary linearly for all of the structures analysed.

For all the structures analyzed (i.e. F1, F2, F3 and F4), elastic constants such as C_{11} , C_{22} , C_{33} decreases with decrease in volume fraction of the first phase (i.e. PZT-7A) for RL-PZT piezoelectric composite structures and increases with decrease in volume fraction of the first phase (i.e. PZT-7A) for BaTiO₃-PZT piezoelectric composite structures (the corresponding bulk material properties of the first phase i.e. PZT-7A are higher in case of RL-PZT piezoelectric composites and lower in case of BaTiO₃-PZT piezoelectric composite than that of the second or outside phase (i.e. RL & BaTiO₃). In case of other shear elastic constants such as C_{44} , C_{55} and C_{66} , the elastic constants found to increase with decrease in the volume fraction of the first phase in both ceramic-ceramic piezoelectric composites (i.e. RL-PZT and BaTiO₃-PZT). Whereas, in the polymer-ceramic piezoelectric composites (i.e. PVDF-PZT) and air-ceramic composites (i.e. Air-PZT), elastic, piezoelectric, and dielectric properties are generally lower than that of ceramic-ceramic composites except shear piezoelectric coefficients e_{23} and e_{21} .

In the transverse direction (i.e. perpendicular to poling direction, 1-direction), all piezoelectric composite structures studied (i.e. F1, F2, F3 and F4) and are made of BaTiO₃-PZT (i.e. ceramic-ceramic piezoelectric composite system) have highest elastic and dielectric constants (i.e. C_{11} and κ_{11}). Whereas, PVDF-PZT (i.e. polymer-ceramic) piezocomposites system and Air-PZT (i.e. air-ceramic) piezoelectric composite system, have lowest and piezoelectric composite system RL-PZT (i.e. ceramic-ceramic) piezoelectric composites have intermediate values. For example, for piezoelectric composite structure F2 (i.e. strut length i.e. $L=4$) with 23.5% PZT-7A volume fraction, various

piezoelectric composite structures such as BaTiO₃-PZT, RL-PZT, PVDF-PZT, Air-PZT, respectively has values of C_{11} and κ_{11} as 149.1GPa and 10.25 nC²/Nm², 120.8GPa and 10.18 nC²/Nm², 14.9GPa and 0.78 nC²/Nm² and 8.1GPa and 0.72 nC²/Nm². In the longitudinal direction (i.e. parallel to poling direction, 2-direction), BaTiO₃-PZT (i.e. ceramic-ceramic) piezoelectric composite system has highest elastic and dielectric constant (i.e. C_{22} and K_{22}). For example, for piezoelectric composite F2 (strut length i.e. L=4) with 23.5% PZT-7A volume fraction, various piezoelectric composite structures such as BaTiO₃-PZT, RL-PZT, PVDF-PZT, and Air-PZT, respectively have C_{22} and K_{22} of 141.9GPa and 10.85 nC²/Nm², 109.3GPa and 4.914 nC²/Nm², 12.7GPa and 0.35 nC²/Nm², and 6.7GPa and 0.28 nC²/Nm². On the other hand, RL-PZT (i.e. ceramic-ceramic) piezoelectric composite has shown to exhibit highest piezoelectric coefficient (i.e. e_{22}) in 2-direction for all piezoelectric composite structures analysed. For example, piezoelectric composite structure F2 (strut length i.e. L=4) with 23.5% PZT-7A volume fraction, various piezoelectric composites such as BaTiO₃-PZT, RL-PZT, PVDF-PZT, Air-PZT, respectively has e_{22} of 15.37 C²/Nm², 17.78 C/m², 0.95 C/m², 1.03 C/m².

RL-PZT (i.e. ceramic-ceramic) piezoelectric composite have shown to exhibit higher values of shear material elastic constants such as C_{12} , C_{13} , C_{23} , C_{44} , C_{55} and C_{66} , for all of the structures analysed (i.e. F1, F2, F3 and F4) as compared to other piezocomposites (i.e. BaTiO₃-PZT, PVDF-PZT, and Air-PZT). For example, piezoelectric composite structure F3 (strut length i.e. L=8) for about 18% PZT volume fraction, C_{12} , C_{44} and C_{66} respectively, for RL-PZT piezocomposite are 97.1GPa, 57.1GPa, and 57.1GPa, for BaTiO₃-PZT piezoelectric composite are 67.4GPa, 39.6GPa, and 39.6GPa, for PVDF-PZT piezoelectric composite are 32.3GPa, 0.3GPa, and 0.3GPa and, for Air-PZT piezoelectric composite is 0.5GPa, 0.2GPa, and 0.2GPa.

For piezoelectric composites PVDF-PZT and Air-PZT, the principal electromechanical properties such as C_{11} , C_{22} , C_{33} , e_{22} , κ_{11} , and κ_{33} are higher for piezoelectric composite structure F1 with no strut (i.e. L=0) as compared to other piezoelectric composites F2, F3 and F4 (i.e. L=4, 8 and 15). For example, for piezoelectric composite structure PVDF-PZT, C_{11} , C_{22} , e_{22} and κ_{11} respectively, increased by 18.23%, 15.73%, 417%, and 18.71% and for Air-PZT, C_{11} , C_{22} , e_{22} and κ_{11} respectively, increased by 825.75%, 681.63%, 615.59%, and 34.99%, when piezoelectric composite structure F2 (i.e. L=4) changed to F1 (i.e. L=0). However, dielectric properties in longitudinal direction i.e. κ_{22} are higher for composite structure F2 (i.e. L=4) followed by F3 (i.e. L=8), F4 (i.e. L=15) and the no strut composite structure F1 (i.e. L=0) is lowest for piezoelectric composites PVDF-PZT and Air-PZT except at higher PZT volume fractions.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Several analytical, numerical and experimental investigations demonstrated that piezoelectric composite structures, especially 3-3 type piezoelectric composite structures have significant potential for a wide range of engineering applications such as ultrasonic transducers, sensors, actuators and hydrophones. However, a comprehensive study on the effects of interconnected strut lengths and piezoelectric material properties on the electromechanical response of multifunctional piezoelectric composite has not yet been investigated. Hence, the present work was focused on developing unit-cell based finite element model to predict complete elastic, dielectric and piezoelectric properties of 3-3 type multifunctional piezoelectric composite structures. The finite element model was applied to four types of multifunctional composite structures with varying strut length and material properties.

Figure 3: Variation of the fundamental elastic, dielectric and piezoelectric properties with PZT material volume fraction in BaTiO₃-PZT, PVDF-PZT, PMN-33PT-PZT, and Air-PZT based multifunctional piezoelectric composite structures (F1, F2, F3 and F4).

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